

**SOCIETY OF INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE
THE PLACE HE HOLDS IN HIS LIFE**

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Annotation: As we know, preservation of intangible cultural heritage is one of the urgent problems of today. This article is about the place of intangible cultural heritage in terms of preservation and implementation in the education system it will be said.

Key words: epic, short story, folklore, story, tradition, plot.

It is known that the culture and intangible heritage of each nation represent the identity of that nation.

Each of them is distinguished by these unique examples of intangible heritage others also recognize them because of that uniqueness. In particular, we are Uzbek the people of foreign nations are our unique culture, which has been going on for centuries and the epics that tell about our past, they know about our statuses. National dress and they know and are interested in our national dishes. Such examples of cultural heritage are certainly should be respected. Also protection of intangible cultural heritage, preservation and transmission to future generations will also contribute to sustainable development clear as day. Because of the sustainable development of the intangible cultural heritage of a nation there is no factor that can have a negative impact, and this heritage is in full service of development does.

Among the examples of intangible cultural heritage, Uzbek folk epics stand out. Our epics are one of the most widespread and large genres of Uzbek folklore. Well what is epic The word epic means “story”, “story”, “adventure”, “description” and “praise” means As a literary term, this term is prominent in folklore and written literature refers to voluminous epic works. The events described in the epics are moral,

expresses his philosophical, religious views, life, customs in an encyclopedic way. Exactly The art of giving, which is another example of our intangible heritage through epics, is one word so to speak, it was created and is developing day by day. Epics today It is closely related to our gifts.

The reason is that our epics were sung by them and passed down through the teacher-disciple tradition. Also, examples of our intangible cultural heritage are in language, performing arts, people's traditions, ceremonies, holidays, unique music and dance art, nature and the universe in the collection of knowledge related to traditional handicrafts appears.

All of these contribute to the development of society in a unique way, as noted above.

In particular, in the direction of music, "Shoshmaqom", "Khorazm Makomlari", "Tashkent - Fargona Makom Yollari", "Lazgi", "Suvora", "Katta Ashula", Olan, Yallas, Lapars, hymns, thermals, and other directions specific to the region are included. In the field of dance Dance schools of Fergana, Khorezm, Bukhara, Surkhandarya have their own place.

Studying the intangible cultural heritage can lead to the following conclusions:

- knowledge and traditions about nature and the universe in historically formed religious imaginations glorified;
- the relationship between man and the universe is described in folk examples;
- traditions, ceremonies and holidays related to nature and the universe are carried out in different periods it is explained that it is increased.

Preservation and protection of intangible cultural heritage objects in our country A lot of work has been done in order to pass it on to future generations is increasing. In particular, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Annex 1 to resolution 222 of October – Intangible cultural heritage in 2010-2020 of the state program for the protection, preservation, promotion and use of objects Clause 5 allocates grants for all areas of intangible cultural heritage provision, strengthening of

scientific and research work, attracting young scientists to research work task is also set. Today, it is a topic of intangible cultural heritage from practical and technical research programs related to the following can be shown in the box:

- YOA1-003. “Protection of intangible cultural heritage among students” of young scientists the practical project for 2014-2015 on the topic of “formation of the system of implementation”;

- with the UNESCO Regional Office in Bangkok in cooperation “Among pedagogues in order to strengthen education for sustainable development international project on promotion of intangible cultural heritage”;

- A1-018. “Intangible cultural heritage and performing art of Uzbek folklore practical multimedia electronic study guide for 2015-2017 iteration within the project”.

Intangible cultural heritage in the research projects mentioned above The need for learning and implementation in the educational system is explained as follows:

- Formation of the cultural heritage protection system for general secondary education and limited to culture and art colleges;

- Intangible cultural heritage and folklore performance art of the Uzbek people such as the need to develop the basics of a multimedia training manual a number of reasons have been cited.

Scientific-research project work on the application of intangible cultural heritage to the educational system Continuously conduct graduate qualification, master’s, doctoral theses and in carrying out scientific-methodical and scientific-research works related to teaching activities helps closely. Indeed, as mentioned above, intangible cultural If our heritage is applied to the education system as expected, if scientific, theoretical and practical works are carried out for its further development, these immortal ancient masterpieces will disappear won’t leave. It is developing and becoming more polished day by day.

All in all, A presidential decision aimed at the development of protection, scientific study and promotion of intangible cultural heritage was adopted.

According to it, from April 1, 2024, 20 individuals who keep rare and endangered intangible cultural heritage samples will be identified and assisted. At the same time, the evaluation indicators of their activity are determined.

Every year, 50 audiovisual works are commissioned by the state to record and widely disseminate examples of intangible cultural heritage of particular importance.

According to the decision, “preparation-teaching-restoration-publicization” of intangible cultural heritage will be developed on the basis of a continuous system. The activities of scientific-practical and creative schools for the comprehensive development of samples will be launched.

An ethno-folklore laboratory will be established at the Research Institute of Cultural Studies and Intangible Cultural Heritage. Starting from 2024, the institute will be allocated at least 3 quotas for basic doctoral studies, and at least 2 quotas for research trainees, based on the payment-contract agreement.

Also, every year from 2024, employees conducting scientific research in the fields of cultural studies, intangible cultural heritage, in particular status and the art of giving, will be sent to foreign higher education and scientific institutions to defend their PhD degrees.

In March, “National Values Month” events and public elections will be held. “Qadriyat” electronic platform and its mobile application will be created by October 1 of next year.

The platform will contain information about the keepers and suppliers of intangible cultural heritage, including status, examples of charity, as well as their list.

In March of this year, the Cultural Heritage Agency launched a portal for the purchase of cultural assets from the population.

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